

RECOGNITION AND STAFF PERFORMANCE IN YUMBE DISTRICT LOCAL GOVERNMENT, UGANDA

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Abstract:

The study set to examine the extent to which recognition affects staff performance in Yumbe District, Uganda. It adopted Cross-Sectional Correlational Survey design. The design employed both quantitative and qualitative approaches. From the sample size of 186 respondents selected, a total of 132 questionnaires were returned, 10 respondents were interviewed, representing a response rate of 76%. According to Blaikie (2009), samples with response rate above 50% are regarded as good. The researchers used both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the data from the questionnaires. Results revealed that Recognition of staff and performance had a moderate co-relation but, statistically significant (a coefficient of 0.592 at 0.05 significance level), in Yumbe District Local Government in Uganda.

Keywords: motivation, motivational strategies, employee recognition and performance

Introduction

Organizations that put employees first and motivate them effectively have a more dedicated and committed workforce. This in turn translates into higher employee productivity and satisfaction (Robbins 2003). One way to motivate staff is to recognize them in the day to day business operations. In Uganda, staff performance in local governments has become a matter of concern despite the several Public Service Reform programs implemented by the government. This study, therefore, investigated the relationship between recognition, as a construct of motivational strategies and staff performance. The independent variable of the study was recognition measured in terms

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of verbal or praise, formal or written, social and symbolic, tangible and work related while the dependent variable was staff performance measured in terms of duty attendance, meeting deadlines, accomplishment of tasks and working overtime. This paper provides an introduction to the study. It brings out the research problem and the objective and hypothesis of the study; it continues to present the methodology used to carry out the study, results, conclusion, recommendation and suggests area for further study.

Background to the Study

Organizations yearning to enhance performance and promote productive work ethics among their employees are said to increasingly adopt efficient motivational strategies. This is so because motivation of employees both in the short and long run has significant influence on levels of employee satisfaction and productivity (Dorm N, et al 1996).

Historically, during the early parts of the 19th century, work force motivation was premised on the fact that employees were driven by the desire to earn the most money possible. The assumption was that people were being motivated to work by money, and would maximize their work output if they were rewarded with extra money for each increment of work. This made elaborate financial reward schemes to be developed across Europe (Fox, et al 1991). This situation was influenced by Taylorism.

In the early 1960s in Europe, the focus of work force motivation in the public sector was mainly from the view point of need-based theories. This indicated that public servants were mainly intrinsically motivated to perform (Monolopoulos, 2008). This perspective was premised on the research carried out in the early 1960s which associated the efforts that individuals exhibit within their working environment with the fulfillment of their need for personal achievement, affiliation and power, higher status, and worthwhile social contribution (Warner, Cummings and Guyot as cited in Monolopoulos, 2008). In that sense, motivation was seen as mainly being determined by individual characteristics such as personality, values, and reward preference (Rawls, Nelson, Perry, and Wittmer as cited in Monolopoulos 2008). In the 1980s, in order to achieve efficiency and effectiveness, public sector managers had to change the approach to motivation, which mainly centered on the provision of extrinsically oriented rewards (Bourantas and Papalexandris, 1999 as cited in Monolopoulos, 2008). Research carried in Greece identified the importance of monetary rewards to improve productivity (Monolopoulos, 2008).

In Asia especially in Cambodia, monetary financial rewards were adopted in form of salary Top-Ups (UNDP, 2006). Cambodia, however, later embarked on new

reforms called “government’s rectangular strategy” which called for 10-15% per annum increases in civil servants salary (UNDP, 2006). In Thailand, besides pay reforms, government also added Non-Financial Incentives (NFI) such as providing housing, and introducing a system of peer review and recognition (UNDP, 2006). On the other hand, China moved away from relying on government salaries alone and introduced the use of “red packages” (Bloom, Han and Li, as cited in UNDP report, 2006). These Red packages were gifts which were traditionally exchanged as an expression of mutual appreciation.

In Africa, motivation to enhance peak performance was initially based on monetary financial rewards such as salaries and allowances (Danish Institute for International Studies DIIS, 2007). Recent studies have, however, shown that many African counties have adopted incentive systems that address social needs (Dambisya, 2007). In Lesotho, Mozambique, Malawi and Tanzania, housing has been provided especially for Health workers, Staff transport facilities in Lesotho, Malawi and Zambia, child care facilities have been provided in Swaziland. Many African Counties have improved working conditions by offering better equipment, facilities and providing better security. Beside, most of the African counties have developed Human Resource Management Information Systems (HRIM) to provide Recognition (Dambisya, 2007). All these are important motivational strategies to enhance performance. Many African counties have also adopted typical training, and career path incentives including continuing development opportunities for higher training, scholarships/bursaries, bonding agreements and research opportunities (Dambisya, 2007). This means that the incentives systems in Africa have moved from mere pay to non-pay incentives.

In Uganda, improved monetary rewards such as pay, pensions and allowances were regarded as the most motivational factor to institute peak performance as documented by Vailentine as cited in (DIIS, 2007). Recent studies, however, indicate that non-financial incentives such as job security, career prospects, improved management, appreciation of work done and improved working conditions have shaped the motivation pattern in Uganda (DIIS, 2007). Performance rewards and recognition in Uganda is now based on Non-Monetary Rewards which centers on the human need for achievement, recognition, responsibility, influence and personal growth (The Uganda Public Service Standing Orders, 2010). These rewards include, but are not limited to: word of recognition of good performance, open praise, challenging working assignments, letter of commendation, presents, mementoes, certificate of merit, concessionary trips, award of medals, cash bonuses and salary increments (The Uganda Public Service Standing Orders, 2010).

Theoretically, this study was underpinned by Reinforcement Theory developed by Skinner (1971) as cited in (Weighrich & Koontze, 2005). The theory provided an

important insight in explaining the researchers' study constructs. The theory holds that individuals can be motivated by proper design of their working environment and by praise for their good performance and that punishment for poor performance produces negative results. He therefore stated that specific goals have to be set with workers participation and assistance, prompt and regular Recognition should be made to ensure performance improvement. In this study, the researchers believe that motivational strategies in form of employee involvement, when handled well, would improve staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. The major problem with this theory is that it makes behavior to become more dependent on the re-enforcers and staff may never perform without the promise of the re-enforcers. Moreover, the theory was developed in Europe and was better in explaining the Motivational situations in Europe than in Africa. This theory, however, still provides an important insight in explaining Recognition constructs.

Conceptually, in this study four were three main concepts. One of the key concepts in the study was Motivation which according Weighrich & Koontze, (2005) refers to internal and external factors stimulate desire and energy in people to be continually interested in and committed to a job, role, or subject and to exert persistent effort in attaining the organizational goal. In this study, the concept motivation meant eagerness and willingness to do something without needing to be told or forced to do so. Meanwhile the other concept was motivational strategies which are related to non-cash awards which can either be tangible and are visible or intangible incentives which relates to flexible working environment. However, for the purpose of this study the researcher operationalized the concept to mean employee Recognition which in this study meant a participative process that uses the entire capacity of employees and was designed to encourage increased commitment to the organization's success. It was constructed to mean - participation in management decision making, representation in a committee, part of a team, suggestion systems and consultation. The concept performance which is the process of delivering the desired output (Ministry of Public Service, 2002). In this study staff performance included; duty attendance, meeting deadlines, accomplishment of tasks and working overtime.

Contextually, Local Governments Act, 1997, places the district council as the highest political authority within the district and has legislative and executive powers. The District Council meets several times to plan and approve government programmes in a financial year under study. The approved council plans and budget activities for the financial years are implemented by technical officers. The extent to which these plans have been achieved are assessed quarterly by the district council and annually during the annual internal and national assessment exercise with the aim of involving to staff, for better performance.

The district has three sector committees which include social sector committee for the sectors of health and education, finance, technical services and security committee for the sectors of works, engineering, technical services, finance and security and finally the production, community services and natural resource committee for the sectors of natural resources, community services and production. These committees are mandated to hold meetings at least after every two months to discuss the performance of the various sectors assess and discuss the plans of the sectors with the technical staffs. The recommendations of their meetings are then presented to council for adoption and approval. This is a high level Recognition of both the politicians and the technical staff. Besides, it was also a mechanism of ensuring employee involvement. These were all aimed at improving staff performance.

The District Chairman is empowered under section 13 of the Local Governments Act of 1997 to oversee on behalf of the council the performance of persons appointed by the government to provide services in the district. In Yumbe District, the Chairman calls quarterly meetings with the heads of departments to discuss the performance of staff under them and also assess the extent of achievement of set targets. This was also a form of employee Recognition mechanism intended to boost staff performance.

The Chief Administrative Officer is the head of the public service in the District and the head of administration of the District Council (Local governments Act 1997 sec 64). This meant that the CAO was tasked with the responsibility of Human resource Management in the district. In Yumbe District, through the District Technical Planning Committee (DTPC) which involves the heads of departments, the CAO and heads of departments (HoDs) review the performance of staff and the performance of their respective departments. It was in this DTPC meetings that rewards issues were discussed and administered. The monthly DTPC meetings were a system which offer opportunity for employee involvement, aimed at increasing staff performance.

Despite all these, staff performance has still stagnated to the extent that the district got penalty in the national assessment of the performance assessment of the Local Governments, Ministries and departments in the years 2005, 2006, 2007, and remaining static in 2008 and 2009 (MoLG, Annual National Assessment Report 2007 and 2008). The implication of this was annually, the 20% reduction in the local government development grants. If this situation is left to continue, many development priorities will remain un-funded and eventually service delivery will be affected

Statement of the Problem

Organizations that put employees first and motivate them effectively have a more dedicated and committed workforce. This in turn translates into higher employee

productivity and satisfaction (Robbins 2003). The government has made numerous efforts through the Ministry of Public Service (MoPS) to motivate its public servants through prompt, timely payment of salaries, duty facilitating allowances and also by creating a conducive working environment through encouraging employee involvement, recognition of outstanding performance and also providing prompt and quality involvement. Yumbe District Local Government has implemented these motivational strategies in the Standing Orders and has further instituted a mechanism of involving staff and recognizing outstanding staff performance.

Despite all these, staff performance has remained low, there is general laxity of staff to perform, and reports have not been timely produced and submitted (MoLG, Annual National Assessment Report 2007 and 2008). This has made the district not to perform well in the annual performance assessment for Local Governments (MoLG, Annual National Assessment Report 2005, 2006, 2007 and 2008). The district has persistently performed poorly as evidenced by the failure to meet all the minimum performance measurement conditions for local governments thus getting penalties in 2005, 2006, 2007, and remaining static in 2008 and 2009 (MoLG, Annual National Assessment Report 2007 and 2008). Furthermore, Yumbe District Local Government was listed as one of the worst performing local governments.

The implication of this is annually, the 20% reduction in the local government development grants. If this situation is left to continue, many development priorities will remain un-funded and eventually service delivery will be affected. The community in the district will therefore not receive the services it is supposed to. This will result into community suffrage and generate discontent.

Specific Objectives and Hypothesis

The objective of this study was to examine the extent to which recognition affects staff performance in Yumbe District. It was hypothesized that recognition has effect on staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government, Uganda.

Operational Definitions of Key Concepts

Motivation: eagerness and willingness to do something without needing to be told or forced to do.

Motivational Strategies: In this study related to non-cash awards which were either tangible and were visible or intangible incentives which related to flexible working environment. It was constructed to include Employee involvement, Recognition and Feedback.

Employee involvement: meant a participative process that uses the entire capacity of employees and was designed to encourage increased commitment to the organization's success. It was constructed to mean: - participation in management decision making, representation in a committee, part of a team, suggestion systems and consultation

Performance: Measurable outcomes relative to stated targets. It was conceptualized to include, duty attendance, meeting deadlines, accomplishment of tasks, working overtime.

Review of Literature

Introduction

Critically looking at the existing research which is significant to the work the researcher is carrying out cannot be under looked (Kompo and Tromp 2006), it demonstrates familiarity of the researcher with the body of existing knowledge, establishes credibility (Neuman, 2006) and above all it shows the path of prior research and how the current project is linked to it (Mwanje, 2001). This chapter therefore presents the review of the related literature on the influence of non-financial rewards and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. It further presents the major theories that guide the study. It also discusses the actual literature review which is done objective by objective especially on the relationship between motivational strategies and staff performance. Finally, this chapter presents the summary of the review highlighting gaps and lessons learnt.

Literature Review

Recognition and Staff Performance

To many employees the psychic income of being openly acknowledged and appreciated equals their material income (Curran, 2004). Recognition refers to officially and publically thanking an employee for something that he/she has done, by giving him/her social honour. Human Capital Institute (2009) on the other defines recognition as practices that acknowledges or gives special attention to employee's actions, efforts, behavior or performance. For the purpose of this study, recognition meant the process of acknowledging the performance of staff with the views of reinforcing the replication of the good behavior or performance.

In yet another study by Gallup as cited in Human Capital institute, (2009) it was found out that recognition was highly correlated to improved employee engagement with both the employee's work and the organization. It is therefore observed that increased employee engagement has a dramatic positive effect on improving job performance and capturing business value. Towers Perrin (2009) further found out that

manager delivered recognition of performance boosts engagement and performance. Psychological Associates and Daisy Foundation (2009) likewise observed that recognition contributes directly to job satisfaction which in turn results into efficient performance.

Another study conducted by American Association of Critical Care Nurses (2005) as cited by in Psychological Associates and Daisy Foundation (2009) still shows that meaningful recognition contributes to reduced medical errors, conflict, and stress among health professionals and effective delivery of patient care. McFadden (2006) while studying American Incentive systems found out that performance based recognitions when given to those who deserve reinforces superior performance and has significant impact on the company's near and long term success. Luthan and Stajkovic (1999) also found out that recognition when provided in a contingent basis in managing employee behavior is a powerful reign forcer to improve performance and the behavior will be repeated in the future. The findings of this study are consistent with the above empirical literature.

Verbal Recognition and Staff Performance

Verbal expressions such as "well done" motivate staff to perform and often costs the organization nothing. Merwe, et al (2009) in their study of employee performance in a South Africa information technology organization found out that verbal recognition ranked last in mean ranking of recognition types in influencing staff performance. It is however, important only if initiated and received in the significant other people such as colleagues or senior management. In yet another study by Psychological Association and Daisy Foundation (2009), it was further found that satisfaction and productivity are most influenced by the managers giving praise recognition and thanks.

Using descriptive survey in the study of staff nurse job performance, Coughlin (2000) observed that private or verbal feedback is significant in enhancing performance. Studies conducted by Engagement Engine (2009) found out that a pat on the back; a word of praise in front of a team has great power to increase employee engagement to perform. Case study on Scotia bank, Delta airline, and MGM Grand by Human Capital Institute (2009) found out that non cash awards including simple verbal recognition usually work best. What matters is that the recognition is awarded for behaviors linked to specific job performance.

Mukasa. (2008) in a study of rewards and human resource retention in selected schools in Wakiso and Masindi Districts in Uganda found out that praise and excellence certificates make employees feel recognized and appreciated and encourages them to continue with good work as a result of positive attitude created. In summary, the above empirical evidence provides a mixed outcome of whether or not staff performance is

influenced by verbal recognition. The findings of this study are inconsistent with this literature. In that, it was found out that verbal recognition encourages staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government.

Social and symbolic recognition

Social recognition in form of team dinner or outing, and articles in a company newsletter and symbolic recognition in form of company T-shirts, company Pens and Mug both play key role in defining the direction of staff performance. Merwe, et al (2009) in a study of employees in South Africa Information Technology organization found out that social and symbolic recognition in form of lunch or dinner with supervisors, recording performance in company newsletter, gifts such as T-shirts rated high in the mean ranking of recognition types in reign forcing performance. Studies by Engagement Engine (2009) found that the presentation of Commendations have great power to increase employee engagement to perform. McFadden (2006) study of American incentive systems found out that trophies provided to recognize performance widely boost the achievement of specific company and departmental objectives and retention.

Luthan and Stanjkovic 1997, 2003 as cited in Long & Shield, (2010) observed that an extensive body of empirical research confirms that social recognition has significant positive effects on employee performance. Wagubi (2007) in his study of assessing the effectiveness of motivational tools on staff performance in Financial foundation for international community assistance (FINCA) Uganda found out that annual rewards or recognitions such as end of year parties have positive relationship with staff productivity. True these can provide empirical evidence that social and symbolic recognition can reinforce performance and this is consistent with the findings of this study.

Tangible and Work related recognition

Tangible and work related recognitions in form of theatre tickets, gifts, certificate, career opportunities, and recent computers to reward outstanding performance is key to staff. In a study by Merwe, et al (2009) of South Africa employees of information technology organization established that employees rated the work related and tangible recognition schemes first and second in reign forcing performance respectively. Luthan (2008) also observed that gifts, certificates, and lunch with a supervisor and executive direct help the organization to achieve its objective and employee productivity. Kiggundu (2008) in a study of rewards and employee intention to quit in Britannia Allied Industries in Uganda found out that certificates of appreciations, thank you notes and praise have

positive significant influence on intentions to quit and productivity. This is consistent with the findings of this research.

Methodology

The importance of research methodology to a study cannot be under looked as it provides the philosophy or the general principles which guide the researcher's study (Dawson, 2002) and also the various sequential steps (alongside the rationale of each step) to be adopted by a researcher in studying a problem with certain objects in view (Kothari, 1999). This section, therefore, presents the overall approach to the study of employee Recognition and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. It has addressed research design, study population, sample size and selection, sampling procedure and techniques. The section also presents methods of data collection, instruments of collecting data, data quality control and assurance. It finally presents data collection procedure and data analysis.

Research Design

This study adopted Cross-Sectional Correlational Survey design. This design was adopted because it is comparatively quick to conduct given the limited time for this study, there is also limited control effect as subjects will only participate once and the large and representative sampling enables different groups to be compared (Kompo & Tromp, 2006). This design involved gathering data or obtaining information about preference, attitudes, practices and concerns from a sample of a population at a particular time. It was a snapshot description of what was happening (Amin, 2005). This design employed both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Through these approaches, the researcher gained an insight on more understanding of the problem by intensive collection of narrative and numerical data on motivational strategies and Staff Performance from decentralized staff, teachers, and health workers in Yumbe District Local Government.

Population, Sampling Size and Sampling Techniques

The population studied included teachers, health workers and traditional civil servants. This provided a parent population of 2,027. This was, however, too large a population to be studied in the limited time and available financial resources. For purposes of this study, the researcher developed an accessible population of 360. This included 8 Heads of department, 12 sub county chiefs, 135 classroom teachers, 55 head teachers, 65 other decentralized staff, 95 health workers which represents 18% of the parent population.

The study involved 186 respondents. This sample was arrived at using the statistical table by Krejcie and Morgan as stated in Amin (2005). This is shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Sample size and Sampling Techniques

Category	Target population	Sample size	Sampling Techniques
Heads of Departments	8	5	Purposive
Sub county chiefs	12	8	Purposive
Other Decentralized Staff	65	34	Stratified Sampling
Head Teachers	55	28	Simple random
Classroom Teachers	135	70	Convenience Sampling
Health Workers	95	41	Stratified Sampling
Total	360	186	

Source: Yumbe District Staff List, Human Resource Section

Sampling Techniques and Procedure

In this study the researchers employed purposive, stratified and convenience sampling techniques to generate the sample size. Stratified sampling technique involved dividing the population into homogeneous subgroups and then taking simple random sample in each sub-group (Sekaran, 2003). This technique was employed because it helped to represent not only the overall population, but also key sub-groups of the population (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). It also made easy focus on important sub-population and made the researchers ignore irrelevant ones. This made the researchers to generate more representation of the population than the simple random sampling (Neuman, 2003). The technique was used to generate sample from other decentralized staff both at the Town Council and the district; two strata were generated representing senior decentralized staff (U-3 to U-1) and junior staff (U7-U4). It was also used to select sample from health workers. Two strata were also generated here representing health unit in charges and other health workers.

The researchers also used simple random sampling technique the head teachers in Yumbe District Local Government. In this technique, all the 124 head teachers in the district had equal and independent chance of being selected as a member of the sample (Cohen, et al, 2000). This was equal true for each head of department.

The researchers also employed Purposive sampling technique which refers to those samples which were biased on the choice of the researchers (Kothari 1999). The researchers adopted this technique because they believed that those people had reliable information that would help to inform the study (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). The researchers used this technique to sample the sub-county chiefs.

Finally, the researchers used convenience sampling techniques for the classroom teachers. This method was employed because classroom teachers were spread all over

the district; it was therefore expensive and time consuming to use other sampling techniques. The researchers therefore collected information from classroom teachers who were readily available to provide information (Sekaran, 2003).

Data Collection Methods

The researchers, to collect data, used Questionnaire surveys, interviews and documentary review methods.

Questionnaire survey method was used to collect quantitative data from classroom teachers, head teachers, health workers, other decentralized staff, heads of departments and the sub-county chiefs. This method involved developing a pre-formulated written set of questions to which respondents recorded their answers (Sekaran 2003). The researcher used this method because a large proportion of the respondents knew how to read and write. Besides a no bias nature from the researchers was ensured and it covered a wide area of the sample selected quickly.

The researchers also conducted face to face interviews with respondents to generate qualitative data to supplement information generated through questionnaires. The researchers had interviews with 2 heads of departments, 1 Sub County chief, 2 health workers. Other interviews were also conducted with 2 other decentralized staff and 3 head teachers. The researchers used this method because they wanted to get complete and detailed understanding of the issues from the respondents through probing and clarifications (Neuman 2006). Besides, it also gave the researchers in- depth information about particular cases of interest in the study.

The researchers finally used documentary review method which involved studying relevant documents in form of reports, district technical planning committee meetings, relevant legal documents and administrative instruments issued from time to time to obtain data which could not easily be obtained through the other methods. The researchers also obtained information from journals articles, reports and thesis. These were reviewed to obtain the needed information for this study. The method was used because the documents contained vast amount of information and provided cost effective method of gathering data (Denscombe, 2000).

Instruments of Data Collection

The researchers used three instruments to gather data in this study and this included; questionnaires, interview guides and documentary review checklist.

Questionnaires are a research instrument that gathers data over a large sample (Kompo and Tromp 2006). The researchers used questionnaire to generate information from classroom teachers, head teachers, decentralized staff, health workers, heads of departments and sub-county chiefs. The researchers selected this instrument because of

the nature of confidentiality of the instrument, its time saving and above all information was collected from a large sample. The researchers developed the questionnaire on a five Likert scale. The response categories were weighed from scale 1 to 5. As recommended by Amin (2005) for its flexibility and ability to be constructed more easily than other attitude scales.

According to Kompo and Tromp (2006), interviews are questions asked orally. The researchers used an interview guide since it is flexible for measuring certain characteristics which were not possible to be measured by developing scales Kothari (1999). This instrument was applied on 2 heads of departments, 1 Sub County chief, 2 health unit in charges. Other interviews were also conducted with 2 other decentralized staff and 3 head teachers. This instrument was also used because it allowed in-depth probing and such officers easily gave their time to be interviewed than filling lengthy questionnaires.

The researchers finally used a documentary review checklist. This contained a list of all documents reviewed. Relevant documents were studied to obtain data which could not easily be obtained through the other instruments Denscombe (2000).

Data Quality Control

To control quality, the researchers attain validity and reliability coefficient of at least 0.6. Validity according to Kompo & Tromp, (2006) refers to a measure of how well a test measures what is supposed to measure. To ensure validity, the researchers subjected the instruments to three research experts to evaluate the relevance of each item in the instruments to the objective of the study and rate each item to the scale of relevant and not relevant. The researcher finally determined validity by computing the content validity index (C.V.I) which represented all questions rated relevant by the three experts divided by the total number of questions. The first expert rated the questionnaire instrument at 35, the second expert rated at 36 and the third expert rated the instrument at 34. Validity was then computed as below;

$$C.V.I = \frac{35+36+34}{3} = \frac{105}{37} = 0.95$$

The researchers considered this validity very high because according to Amin (2005) and Kathuri and Pals as cited in (Oso & Onen, 2009) for survey of this nature validity of instruments of at least 0.7 is considered to be good enough.

Reliability

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), reliability refers to measure of the degree to which a research instrument yields consistent results or data after repeated trails. To ensure reliability, the researcher pretested the questionnaire instrument once on 10 people of the study population. This was intended to determine the internal consistence of the instrument. The scores obtained from the pre-test were then correlated using Cronbach's coefficient alpha since multiple response items were involved. The results are as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Reliability Index for study variables

Variables	Reliability Index
Recognition	0.684
Staff Performance	0.732
Overall Reliability	0.708

Source: primary data

The overall reliability of the instrument showed Chronbach Alpha value of 0.708. This value was considered high enough by the researchers because according to Hair et al (1998) for studies of this nature, Chronbach's Alpha value greater than 0.60 are acceptable. Also according to Cohen, et al (2000) correlations ranging from 0.60 to 0.85 make possible group predictions that are accurate enough for most purposes.

Data Analysis

Data analysis refers to examining what has been collected in a survey or experiment and making deductions and inferences. It involved uncovering underlining structures, extracting important variables, detecting any anomalies and testing any underlining assumptions (Kompo & Tromp, 2006). The researcher collected both quantitative and qualitative data. Data was therefore analyzed in this study through quantitative and qualitative data analysis methods.

Quantitative data analysis

Quantitative data analysis consisted of measuring numerical values from which descriptions such as mean and standard deviations were made (Kompo & Tromp 2006). The researcher used both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the data from the questionnaires. The data from the questionnaires were sorted, coded, categorized and entered in to the computer and analyzed using the Statistical Packages for Social Scientists (SPSS) program. Under Descriptive statistics, the researcher used frequencies

and percentages to summarize the information of the respondents and to describe the distribution of respondents on the variables of the study (Amin, 2005).

Inferential statistical analysis included correlation and multiple regressions, which were used to test the hypotheses. The correlation coefficient (r) was used to determine the strength of the relationship between the independent variable (IV) and the dependent variable (DV). The sign of the coefficient (positive or negative sign) was used to determine the changes in the relationship between the IV and the DV. The significance of the coefficient (p) was used to test the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable by comparing it to the critical significance level at 0.05. The regression coefficient (R) was used to determine the linearity of the relationship (Amin, 2005). In order to determine how much the IV contributed on the DV, the regression coefficient was squared to obtain “R Squared”.

Qualitative data analysis

In this study, qualitative data analysis involved ‘cleaning up’ data from the interview guide, categorizing it into patterns, and then making a content analysis to determine the adequacy of the information, credibility, usefulness, and consistency (Mugenda & Mugenda, 1999).

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Results

The researchers set out to establish how Recognition affects staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. In this section, the researchers present the findings of the study. It is divided into three parts; part one presents the response rate and the other parts present the descriptive statistics and finally the testing of hypotheses.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Results

The researchers set out to investigate the relationship between employee Recognition and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. In this sub-section the researchers present the findings of the study.

Response Rate

In this study, the researchers targeted to collect data from 186 respondents drawn from classroom teachers, head teachers, heads of department, health workers and the decentralized staff. The actual number of respondents who participated in the study were 132 this is as shown in Table 3 below. The researchers calculated the response rate to establish the representation of the respondents and data in the study and according to Wiseman (2002) as cited in Nalwanga (2010) response rate has to be presented in

research results as it presents the validity of the study. Table 4 below shows the response rate of each category of the respondents and the overall response rate.

Table 4: Illustrating the Response Rate from the various respondents

Category Of Respondents	Sample Size (S)	Response Rate	Response %ge
Heads of Departments	5	4	80%
Sub county chiefs	8	6	75%
Other Decentralized Staff	34	30	88%
Head Teachers	28	20	71%
Class room Teachers	70	52	74%
Health Workers	40	20	50%
Total	186	132	71%

Source: Primary data

Table 4 indicates that, of the 5 heads of department targeted 4 participated; of the 8 sub-county chiefs targeted 6 participated; of the 34 other decentralized staff targeted, 30 participated; of the 28 head teachers targeted, 20 participated; of the 70 class room teachers targeted, 52 participated; the 40 health workers targeted, 20 participated. The remaining participants did not participate partly because certain parts of the district (Kerwa, Midigo, and Ariwa Sub counties) were not easily accessible because of floods. This made the collection of the questionnaires from the schools and health units in those Sub-counties difficult. From the sample size of 186 respondents, a total of 132 questionnaires were returned. Ten respondents were interviewed. This presented an overall response rate of 76%. This response rate is considered excellent because according to Blaikie (2009) samples with response rate above 50% are regarded to be good enough. Amin (2005) on the other hand noted that for survey studies of this nature a response rate of 70% is considered valid. This therefore means that the findings of this research are valid.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Results

The researchers set out to investigate the relationship between recognition as an aspect of motivational strategies and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. In this section, the researchers present the findings of the stud of descriptive statistic and testing of hypotheses, analysis and interpretation of the data. The findings obtained from the questionnaire are summarized in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics on the views of respondents on recognition

Recognition	Percentage Responses					Mean	SD
	SDA	D	N	A	SA		
Word of thanks is used to appreciate performance	4.5% (6)	56.1% (74)	7.6% (10)	30.3% (40)	1.5% (2)	2.32	1.606
Written thank you note is given for good performance	37.9% (50)	30.3% (40)	16.7% (22)	6.1% (8)	9.1% (12)	2.14	1.731
Certificate is presented to recognize performance	37.9% (50)	24.2% (32)	12.1% (16)	7.6% (10)	18.2% (24)	2.35	1.642
Performance success is celebrated in a party	3% (4)	53% (70)	3.0% (4)	9.1% (12)	31.8% (42)	2.72	1.596
Gifts and T-shirts are given to reward good performance	3% (4)	16.7% (22)	9.1% (12)	37.9% (50)	33.3% (44)	3.82	1.156
Recognition of staff performance is done in a group	27.3% (36)	21.2% (28)	13.6% (18)	24.2% (32)	13.6% (18)	2.76	1.431
Recognition of performance is done individually	21.2% (28)	7.6% (10)	15.2% (20)	31.1% (41)	25% (33)	3.31	1.468
Good performance is recognized immediately	39.4% (52)	22.7% (30)	22.7% (30)	6.1% (8)	25.8% (34)	2.73	1.799
Recognition of good performance is delayed	7.6% (10)	12.1% (16)	21.2% (28)	39.4% (52)	19.7% (26)	3.52	1.162

Source: Primary data

Table 5 above indicates that when respondents were asked whether word of thanks was one of the approaches used to recognize their performance, majority (60.6%) indicated that word of thanks was not used to appreciate performance, while minority (31.8%) agreed that word of thanks is used to appreciate outstanding performance. and (7.6%) remained undecided. Also, when participants were asked whether thank you note is provided to appreciate their performance majority (68.2%) disagreed that written thank you note was given for good performance though (15.2%) minority agreed and few (16.7%) remained undecided. This implies that verbal words of thank you and written thank you notes were not much used to appreciate staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. This finding is in agreement with the interview results especially one sub county chief noted that *“in the financial year 2009/2010 my sub county performed well in the national assessment of performance for local governments. The national assessment team from the MoLG appreciated our performance. We expected the CAO to also appreciate our performance with letter of recognition instead, he noted that it was our obligation. We felt disappointed. Thank you notes are a mystery in the district.*

Further still when the respondents were asked whether certificates were presented to appreciate their performance, majority (62.1%) disagreed while minority (25.8%) agreed and few (12.1%) were undecided. Meanwhile when respondents were

asked on whether they celebrated success of their performance in a party most (56%) disagreed whereas few (35.9%) agreed and only (9.1%) were undecided. Still when respondents were asked on whether gifts and T-shirts were presented to appreciate good performance, majority (71.2%) agreed while minority (19.7%) disagreed while (9.1%) were undecided. The implication of the above views is that certificates and gifts were not provided to appreciate performance of staff it is only T-shirts which were provided in appreciation of good performance not even end of year parties are organised to staff to appreciate good performance in Yumbe District Local Government. This view is in consonance with interview result where one health worker observed that *“one time I was voted the best mid wife in Yumbe by UNFPA, I never received certificate of recognition from the CAO and though one of the personnel officers’s thanked me in a meeting, not even end of year party were organized. I do not know why I should repeat the same performance in the future.”*

Furthermore, from the Table 5 above when respondents were asked whether recognition of staff performance is done in a group, majority (48.5%) disagreed while minority (37.8%) agree and only (13.6%) were undecided. Also when we asked respondents whether recognition performance is then done individually, majority (56.1%) agreed while minority (28.6%) disagreed and few (15.2%) remained undecided. This implies that recognition of staff performance is not much done in a group but rather individually done in Yumbe District Local Government. This view is consistent with the interview results for example one head teacher observed *“.....we were also called one by one to receive letters of appreciation in District Education Officer’s office. Going alone to pick the letter of commandment made me to continue announcing on the way to people I got by until I reached DEO’s office and back”.*

More to report from the Table 5 above is that when we asked the respondents whether outstanding performance of staff is recognized immediately when task is accomplished majority (62.1%) disagreed while minority (31.9%) agreed and (22.7%) remained non-committal. Meanwhile when respondents were asked whether recognition of outstanding performance is sometimes delayed up to the end of the financial year, majority (59.1%) agreed while minority disagreed (19.7%) disagreed and (12.2%). This implies that recognition of staff performance is delayed up to the end of the year in Yumbe District Local Government. This finding is in line with the interview results for example *“once good performance is immediately recognized, the some performance will be replicated but sometimes we delay up to the end of the financial year, the good performer will see no value in the recognition”.*

Staff Performance

The research set out to generate respondents view on the dependent variable (staff performance). The summary of the responses are provided in the Table 6 below.

Table 6: Summary of descriptive statistic on the views of respondents on Staff performance

Staff Performance	Percentage Responses					Mean	SD
	SDA	D	N	A	SA		
I don't miss coming for work	7.6% (10)	24.2% (32)	19.7% (26)	34.8% (46)	13.6% (18)	3.23	1.183
I meet my time deadlines	9.8% (13)	15.9% (21)	15.9% (22)	18.9% (25)	38.6% (51)	3.41	1.241
I accomplish all my tasks given	1.5% (2)	9.1% (12)	7.6% (10)	39.4% (52)	42.4% (56)	4.12	.996
I work beyond normal working hours	3% (4)	3% (4)	1.5% (2)	30.3% (40)	62.1% (82)	4.45	.911

Source: primary data

From Table 6 above when the respondents were asked whether they don't miss coming for work, majority (48.6%) agreed while minority (738.8%) disagreed and few (19.7%) remained undecided. Meanwhile when the participants were asked whether they meet time deadlines, majority (57.5%) were in agreement while minority (915.7%) disagreed and (16.7%) remained non-committal. The respondents were also further asked whether they accomplish all the tasks given to them, majority (81.8%) agreed while (10.6%) minority disagreed and further 7(.6%) remained undecided. the researcher further inquired whether respondents worked beyond normal working hours, majority (92.4%) agreed while minority (6%) disagreed and (1.5%) were undecided. the above findings indicate that there is high staff performance with most of the staff meeting their deadlines. This finding is supported by the interview results for example one respondent noted *"meeting time deadline is one of the qualities I bear. I remember a moment I produced the district performance form "B" in time and submitted to the Ministry of Finance Planning and Economic Development and we were the among the few districts who got that quarters release of funds and am proud of that performance"*.

Hypothesis testing

The researchers set to test the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between recognition and staff performance. A null hypothesis was consequently developed to

verify the above hypothesis as; there is no significant relationship between recognition and staff performance. The magnitude of strength and the degree of relationship of the findings were analyzed using Pearson correlation technique to establish the relationship between recognition (independent variable) and staff performance (dependent variable). The results are presented in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Showing correlation between recognition and staff performance

		Recognition	Performance
Recognition	Pearson Correlation	1	.592**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	132	132
Performance	Pearson Correlation	.592**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	132	132

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results from Table 7 above indicate that recognition had a positive moderate correlation with staff performance ($r=0.592$ $**P<0.05$). This means that the two variables are positively related. This supports the hypotheses that recognition has significant effect on staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. This implies that the more you recognize the outstanding performance the more staff performs well their activities. This was corroborated with the findings from the interviews where one respondent observed that *“when I receive recognition for good performance how ever little or small it may be a stream of happiness runs in my blood and I will replicate the some performance”*.

In order to determine the proportion of the independent variable, recognition accounts for the staff performance, a regression was carried out. The results are shown in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Significance of recognition to staff performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	21.827	1	21.827	70.062	.000 ^a
	Residual	40.500	130	.312		
	Total	62.328	131			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Recognition						
b. Dependent Variable: staff performance						

Source: Primary data

Table 8 above indicates that the independent variable, recognition was statistically significant in affecting staff performance, $F=70.062$ (<0.01). This implies that there is a meaningful positive relationship between the independent variable, recognition and dependent variable staff performance. The researcher therefore accepts the alternative hypothesis and rejects the null hypothesis.

Table 9: Causal relationship between recognition and staff performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.835	.344		2.427	.017
	Recognition	.816	.098	.592	8.370	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Staff performance						

Source: Primary data

The regression results from Table 9 above indicate that a unit change in recognition brings about 0.592 changes in staff performance. The coefficients above indicate that recognition significantly contributes to the equation for predicting staff performance, ($y=a+bx$) where y is the dependent variable, a is the constant and b is recognition value. The p-value (0.000) clearly reflects a statistically significant relationship. This relationship was reliable and could be used to make predictions hence (Staff performance= $0.835 + 0.592$ recognition).

Table 10: Variations in staff performance caused by recognition

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.592 ^a	.350	.345	.55816
a. Predictors: (Constant), Recognition				

Source: primary data

Table 10 above shows the model summary of regression. It indicates R squared that tells how an independent variable explains variations in the dependent variable. The Model Summary table above, revealed that correlation coefficient (R), using the predictor; Involvement, is 0.592 and the R^2 (0.345). This implies that 34.5% ($.345*100\%$) variations in staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government are explained by recognition, while the remaining percentage of variations can be explained by other factors.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendation

The researchers set out to investigate the relationship between recognition and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. Specifically, the study set out to

determine; the influence of Recognition on staff performance, to examine the extent to which recognition affects staff performance and to establish how feedback affects staff performance. In this chapter the researcher therefore presents the summary of the study, the researcher also discusses the major findings. The researcher has also generated conclusions of the study and recommendations of the study.

Recognition and staff performance

Furthermore, the study found out that there existed a positively significant relationship between Recognition and staff performance with a coefficient of determination of 0.592. The findings revealed that majority of the staff in Yumbe District Local Government did not receive words of thanks and thank you notes to appreciate their performance. Majority of the staff were not also given certificate to recognize outstanding performance. End of year parties were not organized to celebrate performance success. Majority of the staff were given T-shirts and Gifts to reward good performance. Majority of the staff receive recognition as an individual and not as a group. Recognition of outstanding performance is delayed up to the end of the financial year. Discussion is organized according to the objectives of the study the researcher set out earlier. In the course of the discussions, attempt is made to cross reference the implications of the findings with the existing literature.

Recognition and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government

The researcher originally set out to examine the extent to which recognition affects staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. The Pearson correlation findings ($r=0.592$ $**P<0.05$) - Table 4.11 indicated that there was a significant positive relationship between recognition and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. The regression model summary result (Table 4.14) showed that recognition Adjusted R squared was 0.345 this meant that recognition explained 34.5% of the variation in staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. This finding is in agreement with the Uganda public service, performance rewards and recognition which is based on non-monetary rewards which center on the human need for achievement, recognition, responsibility, influence and personal growth (The Uganda Public Standing Orders 2010 p.33). The findings are also consistent with the existing literature for instance Nangoli (2010) found out that there is significant positive relationship between recognition and employee productivity in the Parliamentary service in Uganda.

The above findings are not in line with the descriptive statistics for instance, majority of respondents (60.6%) disagreed that word of thanks or verbal appreciation was used to recognition their performance. This meant use of verbal words of thanks is not practiced in Yumbe District Local Government that This is in disagreement with

the existing literature for example Coughlin (2000) observed that private or verbal feedback is significant in enhancing performance and Human Capital Institute (2009) found out that non cash awards including simple verbal recognition usually work best. What Yumbe District Local Government authorities need to do is to design a system of how regular this can be done and throughout the district.

It was also further found that majority (47%) received written thank you notes in Yumbe District Local Government. This also agrees well with study by Kiggundu (2008) while studying rewards and employee intention to quit in Britannia Allied Industries in Uganda where it was found out that certificates of appreciations and thank you notes have positive significant influence on intentions to quit and productivity. However, much as (47%) respondents agreed that written thank you note was given to staff in appreciation of good performance, (53%) of the remaining respondents either disagreed or remained undecided this therefore means that written thank you note is not widely practiced in Yumbe District Local Government. It is therefore recommended that the district needed to widely uphold provision of thank you notes to staff to institute pick performance.

In yet another finding, majority (62.1%) disagreed that certificates of appreciation were presented for outstanding performance. This agreed with the interview results and with another study by Mukasa (2008) in his study of rewards and human resource retention in selected schools in Wakiso and Masindi Districts in Uganda found out that excellence certificates make employees feel recognized and appreciated and encourages them to continue with good work as a result of positive attitude created. This is good what Yumbe District Local Government needed to do is to time well the issuing of the certificate and selection of the beneficiaries. On the other hand, majority also agreed that outstanding performance is celebrated in a part. This finding is in agreement with the study by Wagubi, (2007) in his study of assessing the effectiveness of motivational tools on staff performance in Financial Foundation for International Community Assistance (FINCA) Uganda found out that annual reward or recognitions such as end of year parties have positive relationship with staff productivity. The most important thing now is that the district should ensure there is clear budget for the celebration and it has to be sustained.

The study also found out that majority (71.2%) agreed that company gifts and t-shirts were some of the approaches used to recognize outstanding performance of staff. This finding is also consistent with the study by Merwe, et al (2009) who found out that social and symbolic recognition in form of lunch or dinner with supervisors, recording performance in company newsletter, and gifts such as T-shirts rated high in the mean ranking of recognition types in reign forcing performance. The study also found that majority (48.5%) disagreed that recognition of staff performance is done in group. this

reveals that recognition of staff in Yumbe District Local Government is not done in a group but rather individually as majority (56.1%) agreed that recognition in Yumbe District Local Government is done individually. This probably would mean that there is no clear procedure for recognition of staff and every supervisor now does what he thinks is good for his department. This finding is inconsistent with the finding by Psychological Association and Daisy Foundation (2009) who found out that satisfaction and productivity are most influenced by the managers giving praise recognition and thanks in a group. Moreover, many tasks in local governments are done by group of people, committees and teams. Yumbe District Local Government needed to institute group reward schemes for tasks performed by a team or committees.

Another finding of this study is that majority (62.2%) disagreed that outstanding performance is rewarded immediately on accomplishment of a task this is consistent with the interview response where one respondent noted that *“once good performance is recognized immediately, the same performance will be replicated. But most times we delay recognition up to the end of the year; the good performer will see no value in the recognition”*. But a good number (59.1%) still agreed that recognition in Yumbe District Local Government is delayed up to the end of the financial year. What remains important for the district is the there is need to profile and categorize performance in terms of those to be rewarded immediately and those to be rewarded at the end of the financial year and this should be widely communicated.

Conclusions

The researcher set out to investigate the relationship between non-financial rewards and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government. The researcher specifically in this study set out to determine the influence of Recognition on staff performance in Yumbe district, to examine the extent to which recognition affects staff performance in Yumbe District and to establish how feedback affects staff performance in Yumbe District. In this part, the researcher therefore presents the major conclusions of the study objective by objective.

Recognition and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government

From correlation analysis presented in chapter 4 and the discussions above, the study concludes that recognition has remained a critical non-financial reward with a significant positive correlation with staff performance. This implies that the more outstanding performance is recognized the more the good performance will be replicated. On the basis of the findings obtained, this study concludes that recognition has positive significant correlation on staff performance in Yumbe District Local

Government. Basing on the findings, the study also includes that regular provision of wards of thanks, upholding the written thank you notes across the district, proper timing of issuing of certificates and instituting good criteria for the selection of the beneficiaries, and clear budgetary provision for organizing end of year parties would further encourage staff performance. It was also further concluded that group recognition is not widely practiced in Yumbe District Local Government.

Overall, the study concludes that recognition is a significant predictor of staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government and the results can apply to all other local governments.

Recommendations

Performance in the public service has been on spot light and this is more glaring in the local governments. In order to justify more funding, there is need for the local governments to show why existence by improving staff performance. This is so because local governments have become the vehicle for service delivery. From the analysis of the findings and from the conclusions drawn above, the following are the recommendations for the improvement of staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government.

Recognition and staff performance in Yumbe District Local Government

There is need to have clear and proper criteria and procedure to be used to identify and select staff who qualify to be recognized. This should be widely used and there should no discrimination of staff.

There is need to put in place a reward or recognition and sanctions committee to undertake the function of timely and rightly recommending to the accounting officer staff to be rewarded.

There is also need for the district to have a clear budgetary provision for undertaking implementation of recognition scheme in the district. This is to avoid recognition from being left to incidental funds which may not be forth coming.

There is also the need to map out all those activity performances that require immediate recognition and those for which recognition can be delayed up to the end of the financial year. This should be widely communicated to staff and will help in ensuring timely rewards.

There is need to train heads of departments and sector heads and head teachers on how to timely recognition staff and on the use of the various forms of recognition to avoid mix ups in rewarding staff which can end up breeding tension.

Areas for further research

There is need to carry out further research on other dimensions of non-financial rewards such as: training and development, opportunities for promotions and work environment. Further research can also be done on the influence of financial rewards and staff performance. This was actually indicated on the last part of the questionnaire by some respondents. Further research can still be done on non-financial rewards and staff retention Yumbe District Local Government.

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